

Simulation Framework for Autonomous Cleaning Robots on Floating Photovoltaic Platforms

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Abstract

As global demand for renewable energy accelerates, automating the maintenance of floating photovoltaic (FPV) platforms has become essential for operational efficiency. However, physical testing in aquatic environments remains high-risk due to unpredictable fluid dynamics and significant safety concerns. This research introduces a physics-based simulation environment, developed in ROS2 and Gazebo, which models buoyancy and tilting effects using the Sirindhorn Dam FPV installation as a reference case. By serving as a critical verification bridge, this framework enables the rigorous validation of autonomous cleaning and path-planning algorithms within a virtual domain prior to physical deployment. The primary objectives of this work are to simulate the complex aquatic environment and to provide a platform for developing, fine-tuning, and testing the sensors and controlling algorithms required for reliable real-world operation.

The development of the simulated environment involved the integration of both the robot and the floating walkway. The robot was modeled by exporting SolidWorks CAD data to the Unified Robot Description Format (URDF) to preserve mass and inertia properties. As illustrated in Figure 1a, the robot was equipped with virtual 2D LiDAR and IMU sensors, with motor actuation managed via the `ros2_control` library. Simultaneously, the operational environment was reconstructed using a dedicated Gazebo buoyancy plugin[1] applied to each segment of the floating path, as shown in Figure 1b. The simulation parameters—specifically compensation and limit radius—were calibrated[2] based on manufacturer buoyancy specifications and the robot's mass.

For robot navigation, we developed an algorithm to maintain a trajectory strictly parallel to the pathway by fusing IMU and 2D LiDAR data. The system utilizes a downward-oriented LiDAR mounted at the robot's center to detect the two edges of the solar panel, allowing it to calculate the

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robot’s exact lateral drift and orientation relative to the panel. This data is merged with the IMU, which predicts orientation changes to maintain a stable heading. To correct any error, the system employs Pure Pursuit for path tracking, targeting a virtual path at the front-middle of the panel. This ensures the robot corrects its position gradually and smoothly, preventing abrupt changes in orientation while returning to the center.

In conclusion, the simulation results successfully demonstrate the impact of aquatic dynamics on robotic maintenance. As illustrated in Figure 1c, the trajectory within the buoyant environment exhibits a distinct vertical displacement compared to the ground-based baseline. Specifically, as the robot traverses the floating platforms, the trajectory depth increases, reflecting the physical reality of the structure reacting to the robot’s mass and downward force—a behavior that closely mirrors real-world FPV installations. Furthermore, Figure 1d validates the efficacy of the proposed control algorithm. While the robot without the control system accumulates positional errors and sways off-course, the propose algorithm successfully compensates for environmental disturbances, maintaining the correct heading. This research provides a verification that identifies potential failure modes, ensuring a seamless transition from simulation to real-world deployment. Ultimately, this framework facilitates the development of robust control strategies, paving the way for efficient, cost-effective maintenance in complex aquatic environments.

(a) Configuration of the cleaning robot and sensor mounting positions.

(b) Simulated environment demonstrating path execution and active sensing.

(c) Comparison of X-Z plane trajectories under standard vs. buoyant conditions.

(d) Comparison of X-Y plane trajectories with and without the proposed control algorithm.

Figure 1: Overview of the simulation framework, robot hardware configuration, and performance validation results.

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